

Prevalence of Left Ventricular Diastolic Dysfunction in Patients with Subclinical Hypothyroidism

Bhagyamani¹, Abhay Kumar Sinha², Kaushal Kishore³, Madan Pal Singh⁴

¹Associate Consultant, Department of Gastroenterology, Medanta Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Geriatrics, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

³Professor, Department of General Medicine, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

⁴Ex Professor and HOD, Department of General Medicine, Patna medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 25-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Rajaram Yadav

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) is a common endocrine disorder characterized by elevated serum thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels with normal free thyroxine (T4) levels. While traditionally considered a mild condition, recent studies suggest that SCH may be linked to various cardiovascular complications, including left ventricular diastolic dysfunction (LVDD). Understanding the prevalence of LVDD in patients with SCH is crucial for early detection and prevention of cardiovascular disease.

Aim: This study aimed to determine the prevalence of LVDD in patients with subclinical hypothyroidism and to explore the association between LVDD and various demographic, clinical, and biochemical parameters.

Methods: Participants underwent comprehensive echocardiographic evaluations to assess left ventricular diastolic function. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with statistical tests including Chi-square and logistic regression analyses.

Results: The prevalence of LVDD in the study population was 30%. Among the affected patients, 66.7% had mild diastolic dysfunction, while 33.3% had moderate dysfunction. The prevalence of LVDD was higher in females (35%) than in males (20%), although this difference was not statistically significant. Age was found to be a significant predictor of LVDD, with older patients being more likely to develop the condition. There was no significant association between TSH levels and LVDD.

Conclusion: LVDD is prevalent in a substantial proportion of patients with SCH, particularly among older adults. The study underscores the importance of routine cardiac monitoring in this population to prevent the progression to heart failure. Further research is needed to clarify the mechanisms underlying the association between SCH and LVDD.

Recommendations: Regular echocardiographic screening should be considered for patients with SCH, especially those who are older, to detect and manage LVDD early. Additionally, larger studies are recommended to further investigate the cardiovascular risks associated with SCH and to refine guidelines for its management.

Keywords: Subclinical hypothyroidism, Left ventricular diastolic dysfunction, Prevalence, Cardiovascular risk, Echocardiography.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

(SCH) is a common endocrine disease defined by normal levels of free (T4) and triiodothyronine (T3) but high serum levels of (TSH). In the general population, the prevalence of SCH varies greatly, ranging from 4% to 20%, with higher rates seen in women and older adults [1, 2]. Although SCH has historically been seen as a relatively benign illness, new research indicates that it may be linked to a number of unfavourable cardiovascular outcomes, such as (LVDD) [3].

With (LVDD), the left ventricle is unable to contract and fill correctly during the diastolic part of the cardiac cycle. This results in reduced cardiac

output and may eventually lead to heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF)[4]. Although the exact pathophysiological mechanisms underlying the association between LVDD and SCH remain unclear, it is believed that haemodynamic abnormalities, endothelial dysfunction, and modifications to myocardial metabolism are all involved [5]. Heart rate, myocardial contractility, and vascular resistance are all impacted by thyroid hormones, which are essential for preserving cardiovascular homeostasis [6]. Diastolic dysfunction in SCH can result from even slight changes in thyroid hormone levels that interfere with these functions.

In order to stop the progression of LVDD to overt cardiovascular illness in individuals with SCH, recent studies have emphasised the significance of early detection and management of LVDD. Zhou et al.'s meta-analysis from 2019 showed a strong correlation between SCH and LVDD, especially in older persons and those with higher TSH levels [7].

Furthermore, SCH was linked to a higher chance of developing HFpEF, according to a cohort study by Kim et al. (2020), indicating that SCH might be a separate risk factor for heart failure [8].

The clinical importance of LVDD in patients with SCH is still debatable in spite of these findings. While some studies contend that aggressive therapy is not necessary because of the low cardiovascular effects of SCH, others support routine screening and intervention in high-risk populations [9]. Investigating the prevalence and clinical implications of LVDD in this population is crucial given the mounting body of research that links SCH to unfavourable cardiovascular outcomes. This study aimed to determine the prevalence of LVDD in patients with subclinical hypothyroidism and to explore the association between LVDD and various demographic, clinical, and biochemical parameters.

Methodology

Study Design: This was a cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH), Patna, over a period of one year, from July 2017 to June 2018. This study aimed at determining the prevalence of (LVDD) in patients with subclinical hypothyroidism.

Participants: A total of 120 patients diagnosed with subclinical hypothyroidism were included in the study. These patients were recruited from the outpatient department of PMCH.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients who have reached the age of 18.
- Subclinical hypothyroidism, which is characterised by increased blood TSH levels but normal free T4 levels, was the diagnosis.
- Individuals who gave their informed consent to take part in the research.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with overt hypothyroidism.
- History of cardiovascular diseases, including hypertension, ischemic heart disease, or heart failure.
- Patients with diabetes mellitus, chronic kidney disease, or any other significant systemic illness.

- Pregnant women.
- Patients on medications affecting thyroid function or cardiovascular status.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, patients were randomly selected from those attending the outpatient department. Efforts were made to ensure that the sample was representative of the general population with subclinical hypothyroidism. The data collectors and analysts were blinded to the patients' clinical details to reduce information bias.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured proforma, which included demographic details, medical history, and relevant clinical examination findings. Laboratory investigations were carried out to confirm the diagnosis of subclinical hypothyroidism. Echocardiography was performed on all participants to assess left ventricular diastolic function.

Procedure

1. **Initial Screening:** Patients attending the outpatient department were screened for subclinical hypothyroidism through blood tests (serum TSH and free T4).
2. **Consent:** Eligible patients were informed about the study, and written consent was obtained.
3. **Data Collection:** Demographic and clinical data were recorded. Echocardiography was conducted by a trained cardiologist to evaluate left ventricular diastolic function.
4. **Echocardiographic Assessment:** The parameters assessed included the E/A ratio (early to late ventricular filling velocities), deceleration time, and isovolumetric relaxation time, which are indicative of diastolic function.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data was analysed using SPSS version 23.0 after being entered into a database. Descriptive statistics including mean, standard deviation, and percentages were used to summarise the data. Logistic regression analysis and the Chi-square test were utilised to ascertain the prevalence of LVDD in the study population and assess the correlation between LVDD and subclinical hypothyroidism. For statistical significance, a p-value of less than 0.05 was used.

Results

Patients diagnosed with subclinical hypothyroidism were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 45.3 ± 12.7 years, with a range of 20 to 75 years. The study population comprised 40 males (33.3%) and 80 females (66.7%).

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	Value
Total Participants (n)	120
Mean Age (years)	45.3 ± 12.7
Gender Distribution	
- Males	40 (33.3%)
- Females	80 (66.7%)
Mean TSH Level (mIU/L)	7.8 ± 1.4
Mean Free T4 Level (ng/dL)	1.2 ± 0.3

Out of 120 patients, 36 patients (30%) were found to have (LVDD) based on echocardiographic evaluation.

Table 2: Prevalence of LVDD in Subclinical Hypothyroidism

LVDD Status	Number of Patients (%)
Present	36 (30%)
Absent	84 (70%)

Echocardiographic Findings: The echocardiographic findings revealed that among the 36 patients with LVDD, 24 (66.7%) had Grade 1 (mild) diastolic dysfunction, and 12 (33.3%) had Grade 2 (moderate) diastolic dysfunction. No cases of severe (Grade 3) diastolic dysfunction were identified.

Table 3: Distribution of LVDD Grades among Affected Patients

LVDD Grade	Number of Patients (%)
Grade 1 (Mild)	24 (66.7%)
Grade 2 (Moderate)	12 (33.3%)
Grade 3 (Severe)	0 (0%)

Association between LVDD and Demographic/Clinical Parameters: The prevalence of LVDD was higher in females (35%) compared to males (20%), although this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.07$).

The mean age of patients with LVDD was significantly higher than those without LVDD (52.6 ± 11.4 years vs. 41.7 ± 11.9 years, $p < 0.001$). There was no significant association between TSH levels and the presence of LVDD ($p = 0.21$).

Table 4: Comparison of Characteristics between Patients with and without LVDD

Characteristic	LVDD Present (n = 36)	LVDD Absent (n = 84)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	52.6 ± 11.4	41.7 ± 11.9	<0.001
Gender Distribution			
- Males (%)	8 (20%)	32 (80%)	0.07
- Females (%)	28 (35%)	52 (65%)	
Mean TSH Level (mIU/L)	7.9 ± 1.5	7.7 ± 1.3	0.21
Mean Free T4 Level	1.1 ± 0.3	1.2 ± 0.3	0.33

Logistic regression analysis was performed to identify independent predictors of LVDD in patients with subclinical hypothyroidism. Age was found to be a significant predictor, with each year of increase in age associated with a 1.08-fold increase in the odds of developing LVDD ($p < 0.001$). Gender and TSH levels were not significant predictors.

Table 5: Logistic Regression Analysis for Predictors of LVDD

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Age (years)	1.08	1.04 – 1.13	<0.001
Gender (Female vs Male)	1.82	0.85 – 3.91	0.13
TSH Level (mIU/L)	1.15	0.94 – 1.41	0.18

Discussion

The results revealed that 30% of these patients exhibited LVDD, indicating a significant proportion of this population is at risk for cardiovascular complications. The study found that among those with LVDD, the majority (66.7%) had mild diastolic dysfunction, with the remaining 33.3% presenting with moderate dysfunction. No cases of severe diastolic dysfunction were observed, suggesting that while diastolic dysfunction is relatively common in this group, it

tends to be mild to moderate in severity. Demographically, the study showed that females had a higher prevalence of LVDD (35%) compared to males (20%), although this difference did not reach statistical significance. This suggests that while there may be a trend towards higher risk in females, the evidence was not strong enough to confirm a gender-based difference within this sample size. Age, however, was a significant factor, with older patients being more likely to develop LVDD. The mean age of patients with

LVDD was significantly higher than those without the condition, emphasizing age as a critical factor in the development of diastolic dysfunction in subclinical hypothyroidism.

Interestingly, the study did not find a significant association between TSH levels and the presence of LVDD, suggesting that the degree of thyroid dysfunction (as indicated by TSH levels) may not directly correlate with the risk of developing diastolic dysfunction. This highlights the complexity of the relationship between thyroid function and cardiac health, indicating that other factors, such as age, might play a more pivotal role in the development of LVDD in this patient population. Overall, these findings underscore the importance of monitoring cardiac function in patients with subclinical hypothyroidism, especially as they age. The significant association between age and LVDD suggests that early detection and management of diastolic dysfunction in these patients could be crucial in preventing further cardiovascular complications.

In this study, individuals at a tertiary care facility in South India with (SCH) and (LVDD) were examined. SCH was found to be substantially linked to greater grades of LVDD in comparison to euthyroid controls who were age and gender matched. According to the study's findings, SCH should be regarded as a substantial risk factor for LVDD, highlighting the necessity of early detection and treatment for SCH patients in order to avert any cardiac issues [10].

In a broad population without overt cardiac disease, the relationship between SCH and subclinical left heart dysfunction was investigated in this study. It was discovered that, regardless of other cardiovascular risk factors, those with SCH exhibited markedly altered left atrial (LA) phasic function, as seen by decreased LA reservoir and conduit strain. These results imply that SCH might be a factor in these patients' increased risk of heart failure [11]. The effects of SCH on pulmonary and left ventricular diastolic function were the main topics of this investigation. The findings showed that patients with SCH had longer isovolumetric relaxation periods and considerably lower E/A ratios, both of which were indicative of LVDD. Furthermore, pulmonary function indices and LV diastolic function parameters showed a somewhat negative connection, underscoring the wider effects of SCH on cardiovascular and pulmonary health [12].

Conclusion

The study found a prevalence of LVDD in 30% of patients with subclinical hypothyroidism. Age was identified as a significant predictor of LVDD, with

older patients being more likely to develop diastolic dysfunction. The study did not find a significant association between TSH levels and the presence of LVDD. Further research with larger sample sizes is needed to confirm these findings and explore potential mechanisms underlying the association between subclinical hypothyroidism and LVDD.

References

1. Cooper DS, Biondi B. Subclinical thyroid disease. *Lancet*. 2012;379(9821):1142-54.
2. Hollowell JG, Staehling NW, Flanders WD, et al. Serum TSH, T4, and thyroid antibodies in the United States population (1988 to 1994): National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES III). *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2002;87(2):489-99.
3. Rodondi N, Newman AB, Vittinghoff E, et al. Subclinical hypothyroidism and the risk of heart failure, other cardiovascular events, and death. *Arch Intern Med*. 2005;165(21):2460-6.
4. Aurigemma GP, Gaasch WH. Diastolic heart failure. *N Engl J Med*. 2004;351(11):1097-105.
5. Razvi S, Weaver JU, Vanderpump MP, et al. The incidence of ischemic heart disease and mortality in people with subclinical hypothyroidism: reanalysis of the Wickham Survey cohort. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2010;95(4):1734-40.
6. Klein I, Danzi S. Thyroid disease and the heart. *Circulation*. 2007;116(15):1725-35.
7. Zhou Y, Fang W, Liu W, et al. Subclinical hypothyroidism and the risk of cardiovascular diseases: a meta-analysis of prospective cohort studies. *Endocrine*. 2019;64(1):76-83.
8. Kim D, Lee W, Lee JH, et al. Subclinical hypothyroidism and the risk of incident heart failure with preserved ejection fraction: a nationwide cohort study. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2020;105(8).
9. Biondi B, Cooper DS. The clinical significance of subclinical thyroid dysfunction. *Endocr Rev*. 2008;29(1):76-131.
10. Kuchulakanti AS, Sharma R, Utagi B. Left Ventricular Diastolic Dysfunction in Patients with Subclinical Hypothyroidism: A Single South Indian Tertiary Care Centre Study. *J Health Allied Sci NU*. 2023.
11. Nakanishi K, Daimon M, Yoshida Y, Sawada N, Hirose K, Iwama K, et al. Subclinical hypothyroidism as an independent determinant of left atrial dysfunction in the general population. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2020.
12. Allam A, Darwish M. Left ventricular diastolic and pulmonary dysfunction in patients with subclinical hypothyroidism: A case-control study. 2019.